

Gluconate Complexes of Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III)

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Gluconic acid (HGl) forms a cationic complex (C^{2+}) with the rare earth metal ions ($M^{3+} = Sm^{3+}, Gd^{3+}, Dy^{3+}$ and Ho^{3+}) at low pH which dissociates to C^+ and subsequently to C at higher pH. The equilibrium constants for the reactions, $M^{3+} + HGl \rightleftharpoons C^{2+} + H^+$, $C^{2+} \rightleftharpoons C^+ + H^+$, $C^+ \rightleftharpoons C + H^+$ and $M^{3+} + Gl^- \rightleftharpoons C^+ + H^+$ are respectively

	1.41×10^{-1} ,	1.41×10^{-6} ,	4.42×10^{-8}	and 4.97×10^{-4}	for Sm(III)
	1.81×10^{-1} ,	1.95×10^{-6} ,	8.69×10^{-8}	and 7.53×10^{-4}	for Gd(III)
	3.04×10^{-1} ,	2.35×10^{-6} ,	1.37×10^{-7}	and 1.41×10^{-3}	for Dy(III)
and	3.85×10^{-1} ,	3.37×10^{-6} ,	1.54×10^{-7}	and 1.67×10^{-3}	for Ho(III)
systems.					

KOSTROMINA^{1,2} reported the formation and stability constants of 1:1 and 1:2 rare earth-gluconate complexes at low pH (pH.2-3) by potentiometric and ion exchange methods. In continuation of our earlier work on the gluconate complexes of rare earth elements³⁻⁴, the present paper reports the stability constants of 1:1 gluconate complexes of four rare earth elements at low pH and the dissociation constants for the dissociation of the complexes to other form of complexes at higher pH.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of Analar quality. The ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 M by the addition of potassium nitrate. The pH was measured with a Marconi pH meter at $32 \pm 1^\circ$ after allowing the solution to stand for 48 hrs³.

Results and Discussion

The liberation of proton during the complex formation remains same when the metal-ligand ratio is increased from 1:1 to 1:5. This indicates the formation of a 1:1 type of complex. The reaction between rare earth ions (M^{3+}) and gluconic acid (HGl) can be represented as

The values of the number of protons liberated (n) per gm atom of the rare earth ions are calculated according to the method followed in the citrate complex of cadmium⁵ and earlier investigations⁶⁻⁷ and these are found to be more than 1 above pH 4.4, 4.2, 3.8 and 4.4 for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively. Assuming n to be 1 below these pH values, the equilibrium constants (K) for the reaction (2) are calculated to be,

Fig. 1.

pH titration of 50.0 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate and 3.125×10^{-4} g. mole of gluconic acid (curve A) and that of the same volume of four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of Samarium nitrate (curve B₁), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of gadolinium nitrate (curve B₂), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of dysprosium nitrate (curve B₃) and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of holmium nitrate (curve B₄) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

respectively which agree well with the earlier investigation².

In the pH ranges 4.6-6.4, 4.4-6.2, 4.0-5.8 and 4.6-5.8 for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively n is >1 but <2. Hence in these pH ranges, C^{2+} dissociates to C^+ and H^+ .

The equilibrium constants, K_1 of the reaction (3) calculated according to the method followed in the tartrate complex of manganese⁸ are found to be 1.41×10^{-6} , 1.95×10^{-6} , 2.35×10^{-6} and 3.37×10^{-6} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively.

In the pH ranges, 6.6-7.6, 6.4-7.4, 6.0-7.4 and 6.0-8.9 for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively n is >2 but <3. Hence in these pH ranges C^+ dissociates to C and H^+ ,

The equilibrium constants, K_2 of the reaction (4) calculated as before⁸ are, 4.42×10^{-8} , 8.69×10^{-8} , 1.37×10^{-7} and 1.54×10^{-7} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively.

The hydroxides of the metals are precipitated at pH 7.6, 7.4, 7.4 and 8.9 for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively.

Fig. 2.

pH titration of 50.0 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate (curve A) and that of the same volume of four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of samarium nitrate (curve B₁), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of gadolinium nitrate (curve B₂), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of dysprosium nitrate (curve B₃), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of holmium nitrate (curve B₄) against 0.05M Na-gluconate.

In the experiment-2 (Fig. 2), the reaction taking place may be represented as

The pH decreases due to the liberation of protons during the complex formation. Most of the ligands would be removed by the metal ions and will not be available for protonation. Hence it can be assumed that the complex C⁺ will be converted to C²⁺ by the following reaction.

Further it has been observed from the experiment-1 that both the complexes C⁺ and C²⁺ exist in the pH ranges of this experiment. At higher pH the complex C²⁺ dissociates to C⁺ and H⁺ according to the reaction (3). Hence above the 1 : 1 ratio of metal-to-ligand, the K_1 values are calculated and are found to be, 1.36×10^{-6} , 2.02×10^{-6} , 3.46×10^{-6} and 4.4×10^{-6} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively, which agree well with the K_1 values obtained earlier in the experiment-1.

Below the 1 : 1 ratio for the metal : ligand the equilibrium constants, K_2 of the reaction (5) calculated according to the method followed in the gluconate complexes of praseodymium, neodymium³ and yttrium⁴ are found to be 4.97×10^{-4} , 7.53×10^{-4} , 14.1×10^{-3} and 1.67×10^{-3} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively. It can be shown that $K_2 \times k / K_1 = K$. Where k is the dissociation constant of gluconic acid⁹ (2.75×10^{-4}). The values of K thus obtained are 0.9×10^{-1} , 1.06×10^{-1} , 1.65×10^{-1} and 1.36×10^{-1} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively

which agree well with the respective K values obtained earlier in experiment 1.

Fig. 3.

pH titration of 50.0 ml of solution containing 5.0×10^{-3} g. mole of potassium nitrate and 1.25×10^{-3} g mole of sodium gluconate (curve A) and that of the same volume of four other solutions each containing the same quantities of the above constituents and 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of samarium nitrate (curve B₁), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of gadolinium nitrate (curve B₂), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of dysprosium nitrate (curve B₃), 2.5×10^{-4} g. mole of holmium nitrate (curve B₄) against 0.1M sodium hydroxide.

In experiment-3 (Fig.3) the ratio of metal : ligand is nearly 1 : 5 and the formation of the complex is therefore assumed to be complete. The existence of the complexes, C²⁺, C⁺ and C in different pH ranges of this experiment are assumed according to the observations of experiment-1.

It can be shown as in the manganese tartrate complex⁸ that

$$[C^+] = [H^+] + [NaOH] + \frac{[TGI] - [M(NO_3)_3]}{1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}}$$

[C²⁺] is calculated by subtracting [C⁺] from [M(NO₃)₃]. The equilibrium constants, K_1 calculated by the equation (3) are found to be 2.07×10^{-6} , 2.73×10^{-6} , 3.04×10^{-6} and 3.41×10^{-6} respectively for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems which agree well with the K_1 values in experiment-1.

Similarly it can be shown at and above pH 6.6, 6.4, 6.0 and 6.0 for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively that,

$$[C] = [H^+] + [NaOH] - [M(NO_3)_3] + \frac{[TGI] - M(NO_3)_3}{1 + \frac{k}{[H^+]}}$$

[C⁺] is obtained by subtracting [C] from [M(NO₃)₃]. The equilibrium constants, K_2 of the reaction (4) are found to be 1.29×10^{-8} , 4.80×10^{-8} , 1.13×10^{-7} and 1.34×10^{-7} for Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) and Ho(III) systems respectively which agree well with the respective K_2 values in the experiment-1.

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PANDA & PATNAIK : GLUCONATE COMPLEXES OF Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III) & Ho(III)

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